

Supplementary Materials

Real-World Safety Profile of Xanomeline-Tropium (Cobenfy), the First Muscarinic Agonist Antipsychotic: A Disproportionality Analysis of the FDA Adverse Event Reporting System

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eTable 1. Full Disproportionality Results (148 Drug-PT Pairs)

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	ROR UCI	EB05	IC025	Sig ROR	Sig PRR	Sig EBGM
NAUSEA	314	7.54	6.65	8.55	5.52	2.44	True	True	True
VOMITING	239	8.44	7.35	9.7	6.41	2.66	True	True	True
CONSTIPATION	110	6.46	5.32	7.84	5.09	2.32	True	True	True
URINARY RETENTION	92	44.03	35.55	54.53	32.76	5.03	True	True	True
DROOLING	30	60.98	42.25	88.01	39.38	5.32	True	True	True
DYSPEPSIA	51	7.2	5.44	9.51	5.39	2.4	True	True	True
VISION BLURRED	50	5.65	4.26	7.49	4.25	2.05	True	True	True
HYPERHIDROSIS	45	6.55	4.89	8.78	4.86	2.25	True	True	True
TREATMENT NONCOM- PLIANCE	35	6.96	4.98	9.72	4.98	2.29	True	True	True
GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	36	6.23	4.48	8.65	4.48	2.13	True	True	True
DRY MOUTH	35	6.21	4.45	8.67	4.45	2.12	True	True	True
GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDER	37	3.13	2.18	4.48	2.22	1.11	True	True	True
SALIVARY HYPER- SECRETION	15	23.77	14.34	39.39	12.95	3.81	True	True	True
DYSURIA	16	7.58	4.66	12.34	4.62	2.21	True	True	True
SUICIDAL IDEATION	18	3.53	2.23	5.58	2.27	1.14	True	True	True
TACHYCARDIA	22	3.88	2.56	5.88	2.6	1.34	True	True	True
ADVERSE EVENT	24	4.4	2.95	6.57	2.99	1.54	True	True	True

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	ROR UCI	EB05	IC025	Sig ROR	Sig PRR	Sig EBGM
HEART RATE INCREASED	24	3.75	2.51	5.59	2.56	1.31	True	True	True
HALLUCINATIONS, AUDITORY	25	25.11	16.91	37.29	15.82	4.04	True	True	True
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	26	15.31	10.4	22.53	10.05	3.35	True	True	True
DELUSION	8	7.61	3.87	14.97	3.7	1.94	True	True	True
AKATHISIA	7	10.43	5.07	21.43	4.63	2.33	True	True	True
VOMITING	6	23.37	10.74	50.87	8.31	3.41	True	True	True
PROJECTILE COLD SWEAT	6	6.27	2.9	13.58	2.74	1.53	True	True	True
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	3	20.47	7.11	58.94	4.6	2.82	True	True	True
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	207.13	207.13	66.85	641.8	32.15	5.99	True	True	True
TACHYPHRENIA	25.98	25.98	10.2	66.17	6.8	3.34	True	True	True
THINKING ABNORMAL	5	7.13	3.08	16.51	2.81	1.62	True	True	True
SEDATION	12	4.74	2.71	8.28	2.72	1.43	True	True	True
PARANOIA	12	14.06	8.03	24.62	7.5	2.99	True	True	True
ANGER	13	9.24	5.4	15.82	5.24	2.42	True	True	True
AGGRESSION	11	4.71	2.64	8.43	2.64	1.39	True	True	True
SCHIZOPHRENIA	8.67	8.67	4.41	17.06	4.16	2.13	True	True	True
MANIA	8	10.55	5.36	20.76	4.96	2.41	True	True	True
HALLUCINATIONS, VISUAL	6.26	6.26	3.41	11.51	3.35	1.76	True	True	True
MOVEMENT DISORDER	9	4.94	2.61	9.36	2.58	1.38	True	True	True
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	3	18.06	6.28	51.95	4.23	2.64	True	True	True
SEDATION COMPLICATION	3	13.98	4.87	40.14	3.53	2.28	True	True	True
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	3	81.71	27.69	241.1	11.64	4.76	True	True	True
INCREASED APPETITE	8	4.82	2.45	9.47	2.42	1.29	True	True	True

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eTable 2. Consensus Signals ($\geq 3/4$ Methods Positive, n=56)

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	ROR UCI	PRR	EB05	IC025
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	3	207.13	66.85	641.8	206.62	32.15	5.99
DROOLING	30	60.98	42.25	88.01	59.7	39.38	5.32
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	3	81.71	27.69	241.1	81.51	11.64	4.76
URINARY RETENTION	92	44.03	35.55	54.53	41.23	32.76	5.03
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	25	25.11	16.91	37.29	24.68	15.82	4.04
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	15	23.77	14.34	39.39	23.52	12.95	3.81
VOMITING PROJECTILE	6	23.37	10.74	50.87	23.27	8.31	3.41
TACHYPHRENIA	4	25.98	10.2	66.17	25.9	6.8	3.34
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	26	15.31	10.4	22.53	15.04	10.05	3.35
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	3	20.47	7.11	58.94	20.42	4.6	2.82
PARANOIA	12	14.06	8.03	24.62	13.95	7.5	2.99
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	3	18.06	6.28	51.95	18.02	4.23	2.64
SEDATION COMPLICATION	3	13.98	4.87	40.14	13.95	3.53	2.28
MANIA	8	10.55	5.36	20.76	10.49	4.96	2.41
AKATHISIA	7	10.43	5.07	21.43	10.38	4.63	2.33
ANGER	13	9.24	5.4	15.82	9.16	5.24	2.42
SCHIZOPHRENIA	8	8.67	4.41	17.06	8.63	4.16	2.13
VOMITING	239	8.44	7.35	9.7	7.19	6.41	2.66
DYSURIA	16	7.58	4.66	12.34	7.5	4.62	2.21
DYSPEPSIA	51	7.2	5.44	9.51	6.97	5.39	2.4
DELUSION	8	7.61	3.87	14.97	7.57	3.7	1.94
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	35	6.96	4.98	9.72	6.81	4.98	2.29
HICCUPS	4	8.03	3.17	20.31	8.01	2.76	1.66
HYPERHIDROSIS	46	6.55	4.89	8.78	6.37	4.86	2.25
ANURIA	3	8.06	2.81	23.08	8.04	2.31	1.49

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	ROR UCI	PRR	EB05	IC025
NAUSEA	314	7.54	6.65	8.55	6.1	5.52	2.44
THINKING	5	7.13	3.08	16.51	7.11	2.81	1.62
ABNORMAL							
CONSTIPATION	110	6.46	5.32	7.84	6.03	5.09	2.32
GASTROESOPHAGEAL	6	6.23	4.48	8.65	6.09	4.48	2.13
REFLUX							
DISEASE							
DRY MOUTH	35	6.21	4.45	8.67	6.08	4.45	2.12
HALLUCINATION,	10	6.26	3.41	11.51	6.22	3.35	1.76
VISUAL							
COLD SWEAT	6	6.27	2.9	13.58	6.25	2.74	1.53
VISION	50	5.65	4.26	7.49	5.48	4.25	2.05
BLURRED							
MOVEMENT	9	4.94	2.61	9.36	4.91	2.58	1.38
DISORDER							
SEDATION	12	4.74	2.71	8.28	4.71	2.72	1.43
INCREASED	8	4.82	2.45	9.47	4.8	2.42	1.29
APPETITE							
AGGRESSION	11	4.71	2.64	8.43	4.68	2.64	1.39
ADVERSE	24	4.4	2.95	6.57	4.34	2.99	1.54
EVENT							
PRODUCT	4	4.88	1.93	12.34	4.87	1.79	0.95
SUPPLY ISSUE							
EXTRAPYRAMIDAL		4.97	1.74	14.22	4.96	1.54	0.8
DISORDER							
RETCHING	6	4.5	2.08	9.73	4.48	2.02	1.05
ABNORMAL	5	4.23	1.83	9.8	4.22	1.76	0.87
BEHAVIOUR							
TACHYCARDIA	22	3.88	2.56	5.88	3.83	2.6	1.34
HEART RATE	24	3.75	2.51	5.59	3.7	2.56	1.31
INCREASED							
SUICIDAL	18	3.53	2.23	5.58	3.49	2.27	1.14
IDEATION							
HYPERSOMNIA	6	3.42	1.58	7.39	3.41	1.56	0.66
GASTROINTESTINAL	10	3.13	2.18	4.48	3.08	2.22	1.11
DISORDER							
DYSKINESIA	7	3.25	1.58	6.66	3.24	1.58	0.66
AGITATION	10	2.95	1.61	5.42	2.94	1.63	0.68

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	ROR UCI	PRR	EB05	IC025
PRODUCT AD- MINISTRATION ERROR	6	3.0	1.38	6.48	2.99	1.38	0.47
THERAPEUTIC RESPONSE UNEXPECTED	6	2.79	1.29	6.03	2.78	1.29	0.37
TREMOR	23	2.62	1.74	3.94	2.59	1.79	0.79
SOMNOLENCE	32	2.58	1.82	3.66	2.55	1.86	0.85
HALLUCINATION	14	2.47	1.47	4.15	2.46	1.51	0.55
ABDOMINAL DISCOMFORT	28	2.3	1.59	3.34	2.28	1.63	0.66
DYSPHAGIA	14	2.3	1.37	3.85	2.28	1.41	0.45

eTable 3. Strong Consensus Signals (All 4 Methods Positive)

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	ROR UCI	PRR	EB05	IC025
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	3	207.13	66.85	641.8	206.62	32.15	5.99
DROOLING	30	60.98	42.25	88.01	59.7	39.38	5.32
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	3	81.71	27.69	241.1	81.51	11.64	4.76
URINARY RETENTION	92	44.03	35.55	54.53	41.23	32.76	5.03
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	25	25.11	16.91	37.29	24.68	15.82	4.04
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	15	23.77	14.34	39.39	23.52	12.95	3.81
VOMITING PROJECTILE	6	23.37	10.74	50.87	23.27	8.31	3.41
TACHYPHRENIA	4	25.98	10.2	66.17	25.9	6.8	3.34
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	26	15.31	10.4	22.53	15.04	10.05	3.35
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	3	20.47	7.11	58.94	20.42	4.6	2.82
PARANOIA	12	14.06	8.03	24.62	13.95	7.5	2.99
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	3	18.06	6.28	51.95	18.02	4.23	2.64
SEDATION COMPLICATION	3	13.98	4.87	40.14	13.95	3.53	2.28
MANIA	8	10.55	5.36	20.76	10.49	4.96	2.41
AKATHISIA	7	10.43	5.07	21.43	10.38	4.63	2.33
ANGER	13	9.24	5.4	15.82	9.16	5.24	2.42
SCHIZOPHRENIA	8	8.67	4.41	17.06	8.63	4.16	2.13
VOMITING	239	8.44	7.35	9.7	7.19	6.41	2.66
DYSURIA	16	7.58	4.66	12.34	7.5	4.62	2.21
DYSPEPSIA	51	7.2	5.44	9.51	6.97	5.39	2.4
DELUSION	8	7.61	3.87	14.97	7.57	3.7	1.94
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	35	6.96	4.98	9.72	6.81	4.98	2.29
HICCUPS	4	8.03	3.17	20.31	8.01	2.76	1.66
HYPERHIDROSIS	46	6.55	4.89	8.78	6.37	4.86	2.25
ANURIA	3	8.06	2.81	23.08	8.04	2.31	1.49

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	ROR UCI	PRR	EB05	IC025
NAUSEA	314	7.54	6.65	8.55	6.1	5.52	2.44
THINKING	5	7.13	3.08	16.51	7.11	2.81	1.62
ABNORMAL							
CONSTIPATION	110	6.46	5.32	7.84	6.03	5.09	2.32
GASTROESOPHAGEAL		6.23	4.48	8.65	6.09	4.48	2.13
REFLUX							
DISEASE							
DRY MOUTH	35	6.21	4.45	8.67	6.08	4.45	2.12
HALLUCINATION,	10	6.26	3.41	11.51	6.22	3.35	1.76
VISUAL							
COLD SWEAT	6	6.27	2.9	13.58	6.25	2.74	1.53
VISION	50	5.65	4.26	7.49	5.48	4.25	2.05
BLURRED							
MOVEMENT	9	4.94	2.61	9.36	4.91	2.58	1.38
DISORDER							
SEDATION	12	4.74	2.71	8.28	4.71	2.72	1.43
INCREASED	8	4.82	2.45	9.47	4.8	2.42	1.29
APPETITE							
AGGRESSION	11	4.71	2.64	8.43	4.68	2.64	1.39
ADVERSE	24	4.4	2.95	6.57	4.34	2.99	1.54
EVENT							
RETCHING	6	4.5	2.08	9.73	4.48	2.02	1.05
TACHYCARDIA	22	3.88	2.56	5.88	3.83	2.6	1.34
HEART RATE	24	3.75	2.51	5.59	3.7	2.56	1.31
INCREASED							
SUICIDAL	18	3.53	2.23	5.58	3.49	2.27	1.14
IDEATION							
GASTROINTESTINAL		3.13	2.18	4.48	3.08	2.22	1.11
DISORDER							

eTable 4. EBGGM Correction Comparison

PT	n	EB05
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	3	32.15
DROOLING	30	39.38
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	3	11.64
URINARY RETENTION	92	32.76
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	25	15.82
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	15	12.95
VOMITING PROJECTILE	6	8.31
TACHYPHRENIA	4	6.8
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	26	10.05
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	3	4.6
PARANOIA	12	7.5
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	3	4.23
SEDATION COMPLICATION	3	3.53
MANIA	8	4.96
AKATHISIA	7	4.63
ANGER	13	5.24
SCHIZOPHRENIA	8	4.16
VOMITING	239	6.41
DYSURIA	16	4.62
DYSPEPSIA	51	5.39
DELUSION	8	3.7
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	35	4.98
HICCUPS	4	2.76
HYPERHIDROSIS	46	4.86
ANURIA	3	2.31
NAUSEA	314	5.52
THINKING ABNORMAL	5	2.81
CONSTIPATION	110	5.09
GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	36	4.48
DRY MOUTH	35	4.45
HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	10	3.35
COLD SWEAT	6	2.74
VISION BLURRED	50	4.25
MOVEMENT DISORDER	9	2.58
SEDATION	12	2.72
INCREASED APPETITE	8	2.42
AGGRESSION	11	2.64
ADVERSE EVENT	24	2.99

	n	EB05
PT		
PRODUCT SUPPLY ISSUE	4	1.79
EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	3	1.54

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eTable 5. MGPS Prior Parameters

scope	n_pairs_fitted	n_unique_drugs	alpha	a1	b1	mean1	a2	b2	mean2	neg_log_lik	converged
database-wide	673567	6781	0.33	0.41	0.0	294.53	0.82	0.11	7.37	3081734.98	True

eTable 6. Signal Classification (Pharmacological vs Disease Manifestation)

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	Class	Reason
NAUSEA	314	7.54	6.65	Pharmacological signal	
VOMITING	239	8.44	7.35	Pharmacological signal	
CONSTIPATION	110	6.46	5.32	Pharmacological signal	
URINARY RETENTION	92	44.03	35.55	Pharmacological signal	
DROOLING	30	60.98	42.25	Pharmacological signal	
DYSPEPSIA	51	7.2	5.44	Pharmacological signal	
VISION BLURRED	50	5.65	4.26	Pharmacological signal	
HYPERHIDROSIS	46	6.55	4.89	Pharmacological signal	
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	35	6.96	4.98	Pharmacological signal	
GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	36	6.23	4.48	Pharmacological signal	
DRY MOUTH	35	6.21	4.45	Pharmacological signal	
GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDER	30	3.13	2.18	Pharmacological signal	
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	15	23.77	14.34	Pharmacological signal	
DYSURIA	16	7.58	4.66	Pharmacological signal	
SUICIDAL IDEATION	18	3.53	2.23	Disease manifestation	Common comorbid symptom
TACHYCARDIA	22	3.88	2.56	Pharmacological signal	
ADVERSE EVENT	24	4.4	2.95	Pharmacological signal	
HEART RATE INCREASED	24	3.75	2.51	Pharmacological signal	
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	25	25.11	16.91	Disease manifestation	Core positive symptom of schizophrenia
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	26	15.31	10.4	Disease manifestation	Primary diagnosis / disease worsening
DELUSION	8	7.61	3.87	Disease manifestation	Core positive symptom of schizophrenia
AKATHISIA	7	10.43	5.07	Pharmacological signal	
VOMITING PROJECTILE	6	23.37	10.74	Pharmacological signal	
COLD SWEAT	6	6.27	2.9	Pharmacological signal	
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	3	20.47	7.11	Disease manifestation	Cognitive symptom overlap
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	3	207.13	66.85	Disease manifestation	Substance use comorbidity marker

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	Class	Reason
TACHYPHRENIA	4	25.98	10.2	Disease manifestation	Thought acceleration (psychotic feature)
THINKING ABNORMAL	5	7.13	3.08	Disease manifestation	Cognitive symptom of schizophrenia
SEDATION	12	4.74	2.71	Pharmacological signal	
PARANOIA	12	14.06	8.03	Disease manifestation	Core positive symptom of schizophrenia
ANGER	13	9.24	5.4	Disease manifestation	Behavioural symptom of schizophrenia
AGGRESSION	11	4.71	2.64	Disease manifestation	Behavioural symptom of schizophrenia
SCHIZOPHRENIA	8	8.67	4.41	Disease manifestation	Primary diagnosis itself
MANIA	8	10.55	5.36	Disease manifestation	Mood episode / schizoaffective overlap
HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	10	6.26	3.41	Disease manifestation	Positive symptom of schizophrenia
MOVEMENT DISORDER	9	4.94	2.61	Pharmacological signal	
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	3	18.06	6.28	Disease manifestation	Negative/cognitive symptom
SEDATION COMPLICATION	3	13.98	4.87	Pharmacological signal	
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	3	81.71	27.69	Disease manifestation	Behavioural symptom of schizophrenia
INCREASED APPETITE	8	4.82	2.45	Pharmacological signal	
RETCHING	6	4.5	2.08	Pharmacological signal	
HICCUPS	4	8.03	3.17	Pharmacological signal	
ANURIA	3	8.06	2.81	Pharmacological signal	
EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	3	4.97	1.74	Pharmacological signal	
SOMNOLENCE	32	2.58	1.82	Pharmacological signal	
ABDOMINAL DISCOMFORT	28	2.3	1.59	Pharmacological signal	
ABNORMAL BEHAVIOUR	5	4.23	1.83	Disease manifestation	Behavioural symptom of schizophrenia
HALLUCINATION	14	2.47	1.47	Disease manifestation	Core positive symptom of schizophrenia
DYSPHAGIA	14	2.3	1.37	Pharmacological signal	
PRODUCT SUPPLY ISSUE	4	4.88	1.93	Pharmacological signal	

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	Class	Reason
THERAPEUTIC RESPONSE	6	2.79	1.29	Pharmacological signal	
UNEXPECTED PRODUCT ADMINISTRATION ERROR	6	3.0	1.38	Pharmacological signal	
DYSKINESIA	7	3.25	1.58	Pharmacological signal	
HYPERSOMNIA	6	3.42	1.58	Pharmacological signal	
TREMOR	23	2.62	1.74	Pharmacological signal	
AGITATION	10	2.95	1.61	Disease manifestation	Behavioural symptom of schizophrenia

eTable 7. Label Concordance Analysis

PT	Category	Label Section	Signal	ROR
CONSTIPATION	concordant	Table 3 (7%)	True	
DYSPEPSIA	concordant	Table 3 (9%)	True	
GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	concordant	Table 3 (3%)	True	
HEART RATE INCREASED	concordant	Table 3 (3%)	True	
NAUSEA	concordant	Table 3 (24%)	True	
SOMNOLENCE	concordant	Table 3 (3%)	True	
TACHYCARDIA	concordant	Table 3 (4%)	True	
URINARY RETENTION	concordant	Warning 5.3	True	
VOMITING	concordant	Table 3 (12%)	True	
ABDOMINAL DISTENSION	label_only (no signal)	Table 3 (2%)	False	
ABDOMINAL PAIN	label_only (no signal)	Table 3 (4%)	False	
ANGIOEDEMA	label_only (no signal)	Warning 5.4	False	
DIARRHOEA	label_only (no signal)	Table 3 (4%)	False	
DIZZINESS	label_only (no signal)	Table 3 (3%)	False	
HEADACHE	label_only (no signal)	Table 3 (2%)	False	
HYPERTENSION	label_only (no signal)	Table 3 (5%)	False	
SEIZURE	label_only (no signal)	Warning — epilepsy caution	False	
WEIGHT INCREASED	label_only (no signal)	Table 3 (2%)	False	
GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	label_only (not tested, <3 reports)	Table 3 (3%)	False	
QT PROLONGATION	label_only (not tested, <3 reports)	Warning 5.2	False	
SYNCOPE	label_only (not tested, <3 reports)	Warning 5.5	False	
ABDOMINAL DISCOMFORT	novel (not on label)		True	2.3
ABNORMAL BEHAVIOUR	novel (not on label)		True	4.23
ADVERSE EVENT	novel (not on label)		True	4.4
AGGRESSION	novel (not on label)		True	4.71
AGITATION	novel (not on label)		True	2.95
AKATHISIA	novel (not on label)		True	10.43
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	novel (not on label)		True	207.13
ANGER	novel (not on label)		True	9.24
ANURIA	novel (not on label)		True	8.06
COLD SWEAT	novel (not on label)		True	6.27
DELUSION	novel (not on label)		True	7.61
DROOLING	novel (not on label)		True	60.98
DRY MOUTH	novel (not on label)		True	6.21

PT	Category	Label Section	Signal	ROR
DYSKINESIA	novel (not on label)		True	3.25
DYSPHAGIA	novel (not on label)		True	2.3
DYSURIA	novel (not on label)		True	7.58
EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	novel (not on label)		True	4.97
GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDER	novel (not on label)		True	3.13
HALLUCINATION	novel (not on label)		True	2.47
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	novel (not on label)		True	25.11
HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	novel (not on label)		True	6.26
HICCUPS	novel (not on label)		True	8.03
HYPERHIDROSIS	novel (not on label)		True	6.55
HYPERSOMNIA	novel (not on label)		True	3.42
INCREASED APPETITE	novel (not on label)		True	4.82
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	novel (not on label)		True	20.47
MANIA	novel (not on label)		True	10.55
MOVEMENT DISORDER	novel (not on label)		True	4.94
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	novel (not on label)		True	18.06
PARANOIA	novel (not on label)		True	14.06
PRODUCT ADMINISTRATION ERROR	novel (not on label)		True	3.0
PRODUCT SUPPLY ISSUE	novel (not on label)		True	4.88
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	novel (not on label)		True	15.31
RETCHING	novel (not on label)		True	4.5
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	novel (not on label)		True	23.77
SCHIZOPHRENIA	novel (not on label)		True	8.67
SEDATION	novel (not on label)		True	4.74
SEDATION COMPLICATION	novel (not on label)		True	13.98
SUICIDAL IDEATION	novel (not on label)		True	3.53
TACHYPHRENIA	novel (not on label)		True	25.98
THERAPEUTIC RESPONSE UNEXPECTED	novel (not on label)		True	2.79
THINKING ABNORMAL	novel (not on label)		True	7.13
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	novel (not on label)		True	6.96
TREMOR	novel (not on label)		True	2.62
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	novel (not on label)		True	81.71

PT	Category	Label Section	Signal	ROR
VISION BLURRED	novel (not on label)		True	5.65
VOMITING PROJECTILE	novel (not on label)		True	23.37

eTable 8. Demographic Characteristics

Drug	N	Median Age	Female	Male	US	HCP
xanomeline-trospium	1423	40.0	442	656	1408	673
olanzapine	6926	44.0	3054	3034	1563	4908
risperidone	6254	35.0	1958	3308	2524	3563
aripiprazole	5516	38.0	2538	2217	1485	3278
quetiapine	9074	44.0	5015	2851	1603	6124
lurasidone	806	40.0	357	163	281	356
brexpiprazole	1288	68.0	705	440	550	750

eTable 9. Xanomeline-Trospium Case Listing (Excerpt)

Individual-level case data (2,132 records). First 20 shown; complete data in repository.

primaryid	caseid	age	sex	reporter_country	role_cod
245940031	24594003		M	US	PS
245948431	24594843	20.0	F	US	PS
246118671	24611867		M	US	PS
246160431	24616043		M	US	PS
246363501	24636350		M	US	PS
246367091	24636709			US	PS
246367091	24636709			US	SS
246407392	24640739	4.0	F	US	PS
246407392	24640739	4.0	F	US	SS
246411161	24641116		F	US	SS
246411161	24641116		F	US	PS
246425161	24642516			US	PS
246427771	24642777			US	PS
246430901	24643090		F	US	PS
246430901	24643090		F	US	SS
246445382	24644538			US	PS
246486911	24648691	43.0	F	US	PS
246499091	24649909	45.0		US	PS
246511501	24651150			US	PS
246511521	24651152			US	PS

Showing 20 of 2132 rows. Complete data: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.19623168](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19623168).

eTable 10. Reporting Completeness (%)

Drug	N	Age	Sex	Event Date	Country	Reporter	Indication	Therapy Date
Cobenfy	1423	52.8	77.2	45.1	100.0	76.7	98.7	43.5
Olanzapine	6926	76.5	87.9	35.1	100.0	93.1	94.4	27.2
Risperidone	6254	65.1	84.2	33.0	100.0	94.7	96.9	24.5
Aripiprazole	5516	69.9	86.2	41.7	100.0	88.9	95.0	26.6
Quetiapine	9074	75.3	86.7	33.6	100.0	89.9	91.7	22.4
Lurasidone	806	57.2	64.5	28.9	100.0	84.1	89.1	23.6
Brexiprazole	1288	70.1	88.9	40.3	100.0	87.4	98.5	28.7

eTable 11. Concomitant Medications (Top 30)

Drug	N	%
CLOZAPINE	42	3.0
OLANZAPINE	25	1.8
ARIPRAZOLE	25	1.8
RISPERIDONE	20	1.4
DIVALPROEX SODIUM	19	1.3
LAMOTRIGINE	19	1.3
HALOPERIDOL	18	1.3
PALIPERIDONE PALMITATE	16	1.1
LITHIUM	15	1.1
QUETIAPINE FUMARATE	12	0.8
HYDROXYZINE HYDROCHLORIDE	12	0.8
TRAZODONE HYDROCHLORIDE	12	0.8
CLONAZEPAM	12	0.8
FLUOXETINE HYDROCHLORIDE	11	0.8
BENZTROPINE	10	0.7
PALIPERIDONE	10	0.7
SERTRALINE HYDROCHLORIDE	9	0.6
LUMATEPERONE	9	0.6
PROPRANOLOL HYDROCHLORIDE	8	0.6
BUSPIRONE HYDROCHLORIDE	8	0.6
CARIPRAZINE	8	0.6
VENLAFAXINE HYDROCHLORIDE	7	0.5
ONDANSETRON HYDROCHLORIDE	7	0.5
GABAPENTIN	7	0.5
ESCITALOPRAM OXALATE	7	0.5
QUETIAPINE	6	0.4
BENZTROPINE MESYLATE	6	0.4
PRAZOSIN	6	0.4
ALPRAZOLAM	6	0.4
FAMOTIDINE	6	0.4

eTable 12. Concomitant Antipsychotic Detail

Concomitant AP	N
CLOZAPINE	45
OLANZAPINE	26
RISPERIDONE	24
HALOPERIDOL	7
PALIPERIDONE	7
QUETIAPINE	6
PERPHENAZINE	5
ARIPIRAZOLE	5
HALOPERIDOL DECANOATE	2
FLUPHENAZINE	2
ASENAPINE	1
CARIPRAZINE	1
PALIPERIDONE PALMITATE	1
OLANZAPINE AB	1
QUETIAPINE 500MG	1
ZIPRASIDONE	1

eTable 13. Full Active-Comparator Results (192 Comparisons)

Comparator	PT	n Cobenfy	n Comp	ROR	LCI	UCI	p	Bonf Sig
olanzapine	NAUSEA	314	262	7.2	6.04	8.58	0.0	True
olanzapine	VOMITING	239	304	4.4	3.67	5.27	0.0	True
olanzapine	CONSTIPATION	110	153	3.71	2.89	4.77	0.0	True
olanzapine	DYSPEPSIA	51	35	7.28	4.73	11.21	0.0	True
olanzapine	DIARRHOEA	30	116	1.28	0.86	1.91	0.23	False
olanzapine	TACHYCARDIA	22	187	0.58	0.37	0.9	0.01	False
olanzapine	HYPERTENSION	18	92	0.97	0.59	1.61	0.91	False
olanzapine	BLOOD PRESSURE INCREASED	15	10	7.25	3.3	15.9	0.0	True
olanzapine	WEIGHT INCREASED	10	432	0.11	0.06	0.21	0.0	True
olanzapine	HYPERGLYCAEMIA	0	31	0.08	0.0	1.26	0.07	False
olanzapine	DIABETES MELLITUS	0	59	0.04	0.0	0.66	0.02	False
olanzapine	METABOLIC SYNDROME	0	40	0.06	0.0	0.97	0.05	False
olanzapine	BLOOD GLUCOSE INCREASED	1	38	0.19	0.04	0.97	0.05	False
olanzapine	DYSLIPIDAEMIA	0	28	0.08	0.01	1.39	0.08	False
olanzapine	DYSTONIA	1	180	0.04	0.01	0.2	0.0	True
olanzapine	AKATHISIA	7	183	0.19	0.09	0.4	0.0	True
olanzapine	PARKINSONISM	2	197	0.06	0.02	0.21	0.0	True
olanzapine	TARDIVE DYSKINESIA	1	104	0.07	0.01	0.35	0.0	False
olanzapine	EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	0	237	0.07	0.02	0.2	0.0	True
olanzapine	TREMOR	23	212	0.53	0.34	0.82	0.0	False
olanzapine	HYPERPROLACTONAEMIA	0	85	0.03	0.0	0.45	0.01	False
olanzapine	GALACTORRHOEA	0	20	0.12	0.01	1.96	0.14	False
olanzapine	AMENORRHOEA	0	30	0.08	0.0	1.3	0.08	False
olanzapine	SOMNOLENCE	32	329	0.47	0.32	0.67	0.0	True
olanzapine	SEDATION	12	183	0.33	0.18	0.58	0.0	True
olanzapine	ELECTROCARDIOGRAM QT PROLONGED	0	143	0.02	0.0	0.27	0.0	False

Comparator	PT	n Cobenfy	n Comp	ROR	LCI	UCI	p	Bonf Sig
olanzapine	URINARY RETENTION	92	72	6.57	4.8	8.98	0.0	True
olanzapine	DRY MOUTH	35	37	4.7	2.96	7.46	0.0	True
olanzapine	VISION BLURRED	50	56	4.47	3.05	6.56	0.0	True
olanzapine	INSOMNIA	28	161	0.86	0.57	1.28	0.45	False
olanzapine	HEADACHE	28	108	1.28	0.85	1.95	0.24	False
olanzapine	DIZZINESS	61	131	2.33	1.71	3.18	0.0	True
risperidone	NAUSEA	314	183	9.38	7.73	11.38	0.0	True
risperidone	VOMITING	239	170	7.22	5.87	8.87	0.0	True
risperidone	CONSTIPATION	110	88	5.86	4.4	7.8	0.0	True
risperidone	DYSPEPSIA	51	33	6.97	4.49	10.81	0.0	True
risperidone	DIARRHOEA	30	58	2.32	1.49	3.61	0.0	True
risperidone	TACHYCARDIA	22	86	1.14	0.72	1.83	0.57	False
risperidone	HYPERTENSION	18	35	2.31	1.31	4.06	0.0	False
risperidone	BLOOD PRESSURE INCREASED	15	6	10.58	4.23	26.48	0.0	True
risperidone	WEIGHT INCREASED	10	420	0.1	0.06	0.19	0.0	True
risperidone	HYPERGLYCAEMIA	0	9	0.23	0.01	3.97	0.31	False
risperidone	DIABETES MELLITUS	0	18	0.12	0.01	1.97	0.14	False
risperidone	METABOLIC SYNDROME	0	9	0.23	0.01	3.97	0.31	False
risperidone	BLOOD GLUCOSE INCREASED	1	40	0.16	0.03	0.83	0.03	False
risperidone	DYSLIPIDAEMIA	0	22	0.1	0.01	1.6	0.1	False
risperidone	DYSTONIA	1	144	0.04	0.01	0.22	0.0	True
risperidone	AKATHISIA	7	145	0.22	0.11	0.46	0.0	True
risperidone	PARKINSONISM	2	93	0.12	0.03	0.41	0.0	False
risperidone	TARDIVE DYSKINESIA	1	65	0.1	0.02	0.5	0.01	False

Showing 50 of 192 rows. Complete data: doi:10.5281/zenodo.19623168.

eTable 14. Active-Comparator Forest Plot Data

Comparator	PT	ROR	LCI	UCI
olanzapine	NAUSEA	7.2	6.04	8.58
olanzapine	VOMITING	4.4	3.67	5.27
olanzapine	CONSTIPATION	3.71	2.89	4.77
olanzapine	DYSPEPSIA	7.28	4.73	11.21
olanzapine	DIARRHOEA	1.28	0.86	1.91
olanzapine	TACHYCARDIA	0.58	0.37	0.9
olanzapine	HYPERTENSION	0.97	0.59	1.61
olanzapine	BLOOD PRESSURE INCREASED	7.25	3.3	15.9
olanzapine	WEIGHT INCREASED	0.11	0.06	0.21
olanzapine	HYPERGLYCAEMIA	0.08	0.0	1.26
olanzapine	DIABETES MELLITUS	0.04	0.0	0.66
olanzapine	METABOLIC SYNDROME	0.06	0.0	0.97
olanzapine	BLOOD GLUCOSE INCREASED	0.19	0.04	0.97
olanzapine	DYSLIPIDAEMIA	0.08	0.01	1.39
olanzapine	DYSTONIA	0.04	0.01	0.2
olanzapine	AKATHISIA	0.19	0.09	0.4
olanzapine	PARKINSONISM	0.06	0.02	0.21
olanzapine	TARDIVE DYSKINESIA	0.07	0.01	0.35
olanzapine	EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	0.07	0.02	0.2
olanzapine	TREMOR	0.53	0.34	0.82
olanzapine	HYPERPROLACTINAEMIA	0.03	0.0	0.45
olanzapine	GALACTORRHOEA	0.12	0.01	1.96
olanzapine	AMENORRHOEA	0.08	0.0	1.3
olanzapine	SOMNOLENCE	0.47	0.32	0.67
olanzapine	SEDATION	0.33	0.18	0.58
olanzapine	ELECTROCARDIOGRAM QT PROLONGED	0.02	0.0	0.27
olanzapine	URINARY RETENTION	6.57	4.8	8.98
olanzapine	DRY MOUTH	4.7	2.96	7.46
olanzapine	VISION BLURRED	4.47	3.05	6.56
olanzapine	INSOMNIA	0.86	0.57	1.28
olanzapine	HEADACHE	1.28	0.85	1.95
olanzapine	DIZZINESS	2.33	1.71	3.18
risperidone	NAUSEA	9.38	7.73	11.38
risperidone	VOMITING	7.22	5.87	8.87
risperidone	CONSTIPATION	5.86	4.4	7.8
risperidone	DYSPEPSIA	6.97	4.49	10.81
risperidone	DIARRHOEA	2.32	1.49	3.61
risperidone	TACHYCARDIA	1.14	0.72	1.83

Comparator	PT	ROR	LCI	UCI
risperidone	HYPERTENSION	2.31	1.31	4.06
risperidone	BLOOD PRESSURE INCREASED	10.58	4.23	26.48
risperidone	WEIGHT INCREASED	0.1	0.06	0.19
risperidone	HYPERGLYCAEMIA	0.23	0.01	3.97
risperidone	DIABETES MELLITUS	0.12	0.01	1.97
risperidone	METABOLIC SYNDROME	0.23	0.01	3.97
risperidone	BLOOD GLUCOSE INCREASED	0.16	0.03	0.83
risperidone	DYSLIPIDAEMIA	0.1	0.01	1.6
risperidone	DYSTONIA	0.04	0.01	0.22
risperidone	AKATHISIA	0.22	0.11	0.46
risperidone	PARKINSONISM	0.12	0.03	0.41
risperidone	TARDIVE DYSKINESIA	0.1	0.02	0.5

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eTable 15. Mantel-Haenszel Adjusted Active-Comparator RORs

Comparator	PT	MH ROR	MH LCI	MH UCI
olanzapine	NAUSEA	6.43	0.66	62.88
olanzapine	VOMITING	5.2	0.62	43.65
olanzapine	CONSTIPATION	4.59	0.36	58.48
olanzapine	DYSPEPSIA	8.27	0.0	inf
olanzapine	DIARRHOEA	1.08	0.0	inf
olanzapine	TACHYCARDIA	0.41	0.0	inf
olanzapine	HYPERTENSION	0.67	0.0	inf
olanzapine	BLOOD PRESSURE INCREASED	12.18	0.0	inf
olanzapine	WEIGHT INCREASED	0.12	0.0	inf
olanzapine	HYPERGLYCAEMIA			
olanzapine	DIABETES MELLITUS			
olanzapine	METABOLIC SYNDROME			
olanzapine	BLOOD GLUCOSE INCREASED			
olanzapine	DYSLIPIDAEMIA			
olanzapine	SOMNOLENCE	0.58	0.02	20.2
olanzapine	SEDATION	0.21	0.0	inf
olanzapine	AKATHISIA	0.12	0.0	inf
olanzapine	DYSTONIA			
olanzapine	TREMOR	0.79	0.0	inf
olanzapine	EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	0.06	0.0	inf
olanzapine	TARDIVE DYSKINESIA			
olanzapine	PARKINSONISM	0.11	0.0	inf
olanzapine	HYPERPROLACTINAEMIA			
olanzapine	GALACTORRHOEA			
olanzapine	AMENORRHOEA			
olanzapine	DRY MOUTH	6.79	0.0	inf
olanzapine	URINARY RETENTION	7.67	0.31	192.33
olanzapine	VISION BLURRED	4.27	0.0	inf
olanzapine	DROOLING	12.93	0.0	inf
olanzapine	SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	1.1	0.0	inf
olanzapine	HYPERHIDROSIS	3.64	0.0	inf
olanzapine	QT PROLONGATION			
risperidone	NAUSEA	4.76	0.0	inf
risperidone	VOMITING	5.15	0.0	inf
risperidone	CONSTIPATION	7.9	0.48	130.97
risperidone	DYSPEPSIA	6.44	0.0	inf
risperidone	DIARRHOEA	1.18	0.0	inf
risperidone	TACHYCARDIA	0.77	0.0	inf

Comparator	PT	MH ROR	MH LCI	MH UCI
risperidone	HYPERTENSION	1.28	0.0	inf
risperidone	BLOOD PRESSURE INCREASED	11.89	0.0	inf
risperidone	WEIGHT INCREASED	0.13	0.0	inf
risperidone	HYPERGLYCAEMIA			
risperidone	DIABETES MELLITUS			
risperidone	METABOLIC SYNDROME			
risperidone	BLOOD GLUCOSE INCREASED			
risperidone	DYSLIPIDAEMIA			
risperidone	SOMNOLENCE	0.66	0.02	26.43
risperidone	SEDATION	0.21	0.0	inf
risperidone	AKATHISIA	0.12	0.0	inf
risperidone	DYSTONIA			

Showing 50 of 192 rows. Complete data: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.19623168](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19623168).

eTable 16. Time-to-Onset Summary Statistics

PT
Vomiting
Nausea
Constipation
Dizziness
Dyspepsia
Hyperhidrosis
Urinary retention
Abdominal pain upper
Vision blurred
Somnolence
Dry mouth
Fatigue
Insomnia
Abdominal discomfort
Headache
Gastroesophageal reflux disease
Off label use
Tremor
Drooling
Dysuria
Diarrhoea
Hallucination, auditory
Heart rate increased
Blood pressure increased
Feeling abnormal
Anxiety
Suicidal ideation
Dysphagia
Treatment noncompliance
Brain fog
Asthenia
Malaise
Hallucination
Hypertension
Hallucination, visual
Salivary hypersecretion
Tachycardia
Paranoia

PT

Condition aggravated
Dysphonia

Showing 40 of 195 rows. Complete data: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.19623168](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19623168).

eTable 17. Weibull Time-to-Onset Parameters

shape	scale	median_tto	mean_tto	n_fitted	pct_early	pct_intermediate	pct_late	hazard_pattern	pt	n_reports
0.59	15.68	2.0	18.4	61	90.32	7.53	2.15	decreasing	Vomiting	93
0.59	11.73	1.0	14.21	60	91.01	7.87	1.12	decreasing	Nausea	89
0.66	10.48	1.0	10.26	32	93.62	6.38	0.0	decreasing	Constipation	47
0.56	15.44	1.0	19.14	21	91.43	5.71	2.86	decreasing	Dizziness	35
0.85	11.14	3.0	8.65	22	93.55	6.45	0.0	decreasing	Dyspepsia	31
0.71	8.77	0.5	5.79	12	95.83	4.17	0.0	decreasing	Hyperhidrosis	24
0.91	4.34	0.0	2.0	10	100.0	0.0	0.0	decreasing	Urinary retention	23

eTable 18. Sensitivity Analysis Comparison (Top 20 Signals)

PT	ROR Primary	Sig	ROR PS	Sig	ROR US	Sig	ROR HCP	Sig
DROOLING	61.29	3	61.29	3	55.84	3	65.37	3
URINARY	42.16	3	42.16	3	70.24	3	48.61	3
RETENTION								
AMPHETAMINES	208.16	3	208.16	3	138.16	3	677.62	3
POSITIVE								
HALLUCINATION	25.24	3	25.24	3	41.25	3	17.72	3
AUDITORY								
VIOLENCE-	82.12	3	82.12	3	100.69	3		0
RELATED								
SYMPTOM								
SALIVARY	23.89	3	23.89	3	40.14	3	28.66	3
HYPERSECRE-								
TION								
VOMITING	23.49	3	23.49	3	21.99	3	55.32	3
PROJECTILE								
TACHYPHRENIA	26.11	3	26.11	3	25.73	3		0
PSYCHOTIC	15.38	3	15.38	3	25.89	3	18.04	3
DISORDER								
PARANOIA	14.13	3	14.13	3	17.12	3	14.65	3
INTRUSIVE	20.57	3	20.57	3	29.85	3		0
THOUGHTS								
NEGATIVE	18.15	3	18.15	3		0		0
THOUGHTS								
MANIA	10.6	3	10.6	3	14.09	3	12.07	3
AKATHISIA	10.48	3	10.48	3	15.28	3		0
ANGER	9.28	3	9.28	3	9.45	3	12.58	3
SEDATION	14.05	3	14.05	3	26.17	3	18.7	3
COMPLICA-								
TION								
SCHIZOPHRENIA	8.72	3	8.72	3	25.48	3	9.4	3
VOMITING	8.49	3	8.49	3	10.44	3	8.16	3
DYSURIA	7.62	3	7.62	3	9.8	3		0
DYSPEPSIA	7.23	3	7.23	3	8.26	3	4.04	3

eTable 19. Primary Suspect Only Disproportionality

PT	n	ROR	LCI	UCI
WRONG TECHNIQUE IN PRODUCT USAGE PROCESS	5	0.33	0.14	0.76
SEIZURE	4	0.42	0.17	1.06
GAIT DISTURBANCE	5	0.48	0.21	1.11
VOMITING	239	8.49	7.39	9.76
HYPERHIDROSIS	46	6.58	4.91	8.82
ABDOMINAL DISCOMFORT	28	2.31	1.6	3.35
BLEPHAROSPASM	3	3.56	1.25	10.18
THROAT TIGHTNESS	3	2.1	0.73	6.0
TACHYPHRENIA	4	26.11	10.25	66.5
MANIA	8	10.6	5.39	20.86
AGITATION	10	2.97	1.62	5.45
ADVERSE DRUG REACTION	9	1.15	0.61	2.18
SOMNOLENCE	32	2.6	1.83	3.68
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	3	208.16	67.18	644.98
DRUG INEFFECTIVE	33	0.39	0.28	0.55
THERAPY NON-RESPONDER	8	1.59	0.81	3.11
PRODUCT DOSE OMISSION ISSUE	13	0.25	0.15	0.43
PRURITUS	6	0.17	0.08	0.36
VISION BLURRED	50	5.68	4.29	7.52
ABDOMINAL PAIN	14	0.86	0.51	1.44
DECREASED APPETITE	16	0.92	0.57	1.5
FEELING ABNORMAL	12	1.08	0.62	1.88
HEART RATE INCREASED	24	3.77	2.53	5.62
COMPLETED SUICIDE	5	1.8	0.78	4.17
HOT FLUSH	4	0.51	0.2	1.28
POLLAKIURIA	4	1.65	0.65	4.16
THERAPEUTIC RESPONSE UNEXPECTED	6	2.8	1.3	6.06
PRODUCT USE COMPLAINT	4	1.88	0.75	4.75
LIMB DISCOMFORT	3	1.68	0.59	4.81
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	3	20.57	7.15	59.23

Showing 30 of 147 rows. Complete data: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.19623168](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19623168).

eTable 20. US Reports Only Disproportionality

PT	n	ROR	LCI	UCI
SOMNOLENCE	31	3.03	2.13	4.32
ADVERSE DRUG REACTION	9	0.91	0.48	1.73
AGITATION	10	4.26	2.32	7.84
MANIA	8	14.09	7.14	27.81
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	3	138.16	44.59	428.1
DIARRHOEA	29	0.66	0.46	0.95
DIZZINESS	61	2.18	1.69	2.82
LETHARGY	4	1.48	0.59	3.75
RETCHING	6	3.96	1.83	8.57
HYPERMOMNIA	6	3.16	1.46	6.84
IRRITABILITY	5	2.0	0.86	4.62
PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION ISSUE	3	1.26	0.44	3.6
VERTIGO	4	1.62	0.64	4.1
SLEEP DISORDER	4	0.95	0.38	2.4
COLD SWEAT	6	8.79	4.05	19.07
INSOMNIA	27	1.94	1.33	2.83
NAUSEA	311	7.88	6.94	8.94
GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDER	27	3.42	2.34	4.99
WEIGHT DECREASED	23	1.45	0.96	2.17
PARANOIA	12	17.12	9.75	30.04
PRODUCT ADMINISTRATION ERROR	6	2.8	1.3	6.07
MUSCLE TWITCHING	3	3.54	1.24	10.13
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	35	8.15	5.83	11.39
SCHIZOPHRENIA	7	25.48	12.3	52.77
PAIN	3	0.1	0.03	0.27
PHARYNGEAL SWELLING	3	2.86	1.0	8.17
DRUG INTOLERANCE	8	1.69	0.86	3.31
URINARY RETENTION	90	70.24	56.34	87.58
DYSPEPSIA	51	8.26	6.24	10.92
THERAPEUTIC RESPONSE DECREASED	4	0.84	0.33	2.13

Showing 30 of 146 rows. Complete data: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.19623168](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19623168).

eTable 21. HCP Reporters Only Disproportionality

PT	n	ROR	LCI	UCI
CONDITION AGGRAVATED	8	0.37	0.19	0.73
MUSCULAR WEAKNESS	4	1.34	0.53	3.38
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	18	18.04	11.33	28.72
PALPITATIONS	5	2.0	0.86	4.63
HALLUCINATION	4	2.3	0.91	5.81
HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	3	4.5	1.57	12.89
ANGER	4	12.58	4.96	31.94
SEDATION COMPLICATION	3	18.7	6.49	53.86
DRUG INTERACTION	3	0.47	0.17	1.35
NIGHT SWEATS	5	3.79	1.64	8.79
FATIGUE	7	0.38	0.19	0.79
HYPERSENSITIVITY	3	0.54	0.19	1.54
TREMOR	8	2.44	1.24	4.8
MEMORY IMPAIRMENT	4	1.72	0.68	4.35
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	10	28.66	15.48	53.07
DYSPHAGIA	4	1.26	0.5	3.2
ABDOMINAL PAIN UPPER	7	1.51	0.74	3.11
HYPERTENSION	10	1.21	0.66	2.23
ANXIETY	4	0.83	0.33	2.1
CONSTIPATION	49	10.01	7.49	13.38
INCREASED APPETITE	5	16.62	7.14	38.67
HICCUPS	3	13.96	4.85	40.12
SUICIDAL IDEATION	10	4.56	2.48	8.4
DYSPEPSIA	10	4.04	2.19	7.44
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	20	7.48	4.81	11.61
SCHIZOPHRENIA	6	9.4	4.33	20.4
DRUG INTOLERANCE	9	1.99	1.05	3.78
URINARY RETENTION	53	48.61	36.62	64.53
OFF LABEL USE	58	0.93	0.72	1.22
DEATH	6	0.28	0.13	0.6

Showing 30 of 87 rows. Complete data: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.19623168](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19623168).

eTable 22. Serious Reports Only

PT	n	ROR	LCI	UCI	Signal
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	1				False
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	1				False
DROOLING	1				False
URINARY RETENTION	9	29.94	15.44	58.06	True
TACHYPHRENIA	0				False
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	5	44.07	18.68	103.94	True
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	2				False
VOMITING PROJECTILE	0				False
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	1				False
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	1				False
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	11	36.85	20.07	67.63	True
PARANOIA	1				False
SEDATION COMPLICATION	0				False
MANIA	3	26.51	9.13	76.91	True
AKATHISIA	0				False
ANGER	0				False
SCHIZOPHRENIA	3	15.55	5.37	45.06	True
VOMITING	21	5.05	3.18	8.02	True
ANURIA	0				False
HICCUPS	1				False
DELUSION	0				False
DYSURIA	2				False
NAUSEA	21	4.75	2.99	7.54	True
DYSPEPSIA	1				False
THINKING ABNORMAL	0				False
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	1				False
HYPERHIDROSIS	1				False
CONSTIPATION	12	7.6	4.24	13.62	True
COLD SWEAT	0				False
HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	2				False
GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	2				False
DRY MOUTH	2				False
VISION BLURRED	4	7.85	3.06	20.11	True
EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	0				False
MOVEMENT DISORDER	0				False
PRODUCT SUPPLY ISSUE	0				False
INCREASED APPETITE	0				False
SEDATION	1				False

PT	n	ROR	LCI	UCI	Signal
AGGRESSION	1				False
RETCHING	1				False
ADVERSE EVENT	0				False
ABNORMAL BEHAVIOUR	1				False
TACHYCARDIA	3	3.2	1.11	9.26	True
HEART RATE INCREASED	1				False
SUICIDAL IDEATION	7	10.68	5.1	22.33	True
HYPERSOMNIA	0				False
DYSKINESIA	0				False
GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDER	0				False
PRODUCT ADMINISTRATION ERROR	1				False
AGITATION	0				False
THERAPEUTIC RESPONSE UNEXPECTED	1				False
TREMOR	1				False
SOMNOLENCE	2				False
HALLUCINATION	4	8.01	3.13	20.52	True
ABDOMINAL DISCOMFORT	4	3.49	1.36	8.94	True
DYSPHAGIA	3	4.23	1.46	12.24	True

eTable 23. Monotherapy (Polypharmacy Excluded)

PT	n	ROR	LCI	UCI	Signal
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	2				False
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	2				False
DROOLING	27	59.98	40.8	88.2	True
URINARY RETENTION	80	41.7	33.18	52.4	True
TACHYPHRENIA	4	28.49	11.19	72.57	True
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	23	25.34	16.79	38.24	True
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	13	22.63	13.18	38.85	True
VOMITING PROJECTILE	6	25.64	11.78	55.8	True
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	3	22.45	7.8	64.63	True
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	3	19.81	6.89	56.97	True
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	22	14.2	9.34	21.59	True
PARANOIA	9	11.67	6.15	22.15	True
SEDATION COMPLICATION	3	15.33	5.34	44.02	True
MANIA	4	6.08	2.41	15.38	True
AKATHISIA	5	8.35	3.61	19.35	True
ANGER	10	7.85	4.27	14.44	True
SCHIZOPHRENIA	6	7.25	3.35	15.71	True
VOMITING	225	8.77	7.59	10.13	True
ANURIA	2				False
HICCUPS	4	8.8	3.48	22.28	True
DELUSION	6	6.37	2.94	13.79	True
DYSURIA	16	8.32	5.11	13.54	True
NAUSEA	291	7.7	6.76	8.77	True
DYSPEPSIA	49	7.6	5.71	10.1	True
THINKING ABNORMAL	4	6.39	2.53	16.15	True
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	33	7.2	5.11	10.16	True
HYPERHIDROSIS	43	6.72	4.96	9.1	True
CONSTIPATION	90	5.74	4.64	7.11	True
COLD SWEAT	6	6.88	3.18	14.9	True
HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	10	6.87	3.74	12.63	True
GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	29	5.49	3.81	7.92	True
DRY MOUTH	33	6.43	4.56	9.07	True
VISION BLURRED	47	5.83	4.36	7.8	True
EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	3	5.45	1.91	15.59	True
MOVEMENT DISORDER	8	4.84	2.46	9.52	True
PRODUCT SUPPLY ISSUE	3	4.16	1.45	11.89	True
INCREASED APPETITE	5	3.41	1.47	7.88	True
SEDATION	10	4.36	2.37	8.01	True

PT	n	ROR	LCI	UCI	Signal
AGGRESSION	11	5.17	2.89	9.25	True
RETCHING	5	4.17	1.8	9.64	True
ADVERSE EVENT	24	4.83	3.24	7.22	True
ABNORMAL BEHAVIOUR	4	3.79	1.5	9.59	True
TACHYCARDIA	17	3.3	2.06	5.29	True
HEART RATE INCREASED	19	3.26	2.08	5.1	True
SUICIDAL IDEATION	17	3.66	2.28	5.87	True
HYPERSOMNIA	6	3.75	1.73	8.11	True
DYSKINESIA	6	3.08	1.43	6.67	True
GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDER	28	3.2	2.21	4.64	True
PRODUCT ADMINISTRATION ERROR	6	3.29	1.52	7.11	True
AGITATION	8	2.62	1.33	5.14	True
THERAPEUTIC RESPONSE UNEXPECTED	5	2.59	1.12	5.98	True
TREMOR	18	2.26	1.42	3.57	True
SOMNOLENCE	32	2.84	2.0	4.02	True
HALLUCINATION	12	2.33	1.34	4.07	True
ABDOMINAL DISCOMFORT	24	2.17	1.45	3.23	True
DYSPHAGIA	13	2.34	1.37	4.01	True

eTable 24. Weber Effect Quarterly Assessment

Quarter	Reports	Unique PTs
2024Q4	156	112
2025Q1	325	202
2025Q2	294	175
2025Q3	318	204
2025Q4	330	220

eTable 25. Indication-Restricted (Schizophrenia Only)

PT	n	ROR	LCI	UCI
CONDITION AGGRAVATED	8	0.44	0.22	0.86
PALPITATIONS	8	1.99	1.01	3.92
HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	8	8.35	4.24	16.43
HALLUCINATION	10	2.95	1.6	5.42
MUSCULAR WEAKNESS	7	1.65	0.8	3.38
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	18	17.56	11.06	27.89
THINKING ABNORMAL	3	7.45	2.6	21.32
LETHARGY	4	2.34	0.93	5.91
DIZZINESS	46	2.5	1.86	3.36
DIARRHOEA	20	0.68	0.44	1.06
RETCHING	4	5.12	2.02	12.94
IRRITABILITY	4	2.56	1.01	6.48
COLD SWEAT	3	5.54	1.94	15.85
NAUSEA	198	7.9	6.74	9.26
INSOMNIA	18	1.98	1.25	3.14
GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDER	13	2.26	1.32	3.87
WEIGHT DECREASED	11	0.96	0.54	1.72
PRODUCT ADMINISTRATION ERROR	4	3.41	1.35	8.62
PARANOIA	10	19.46	10.56	35.87
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	3	29.76	10.34	85.66
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	15	24.92	15.03	41.29
RESTLESSNESS	3	2.84	0.99	8.13
SPEECH DISORDER	3	1.97	0.69	5.63
PRODUCT DOSE OMISSION ISSUE	4	0.14	0.05	0.35
DRUG INEFFECTIVE	17	0.33	0.21	0.54
PRURITUS	3	0.15	0.05	0.42
VISION BLURRED	34	6.37	4.53	8.96
ABDOMINAL PAIN	8	0.82	0.42	1.61
LIMB DISCOMFORT	3	2.76	0.97	7.89
HEART RATE INCREASED	16	4.16	2.55	6.77

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eTable 26. COVID Co-Reporting Exclusion

covid_coreports	total	pct
0	1423	0

eTable 27. Sex-Stratified Disproportionality

sex	pt	a	ror	ror_lower95	ror_upper95	signal
Female	AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	0				False
Female	VIOLENCE- RELATED SYMPTOM	1				False
Female	DROOLING	18	143.59	88.78	232.24	True
Female	URINARY RETENTION	28	54.65	37.22	80.25	True
Female	TACHYPHRENIA	1				False
Female	HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	10	34.38	18.54	63.73	True
Female	SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	8	45.33	22.82	90.03	True
Female	VOMITING PROJECTILE	3	28.38	9.84	81.84	True
Female	INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	0				False
Female	NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	0				False
Female	PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	6	13.43	6.17	29.2	True
Female	PARANOIA	4	18.6	7.32	47.28	True
Female	SEDATION COMPLICATION	0				False
Female	MANIA	4	16.45	6.47	41.8	True
Female	AKATHISIA	4	20.19	7.94	51.35	True
Female	ANGER	3	8.22	2.87	23.6	True
Female	SCHIZOPHRENIA	2				False
Female	VOMITING	96	9.08	7.24	11.38	True
Female	ANURIA	1				False
Female	HICCUPS	2				False
Female	DELUSION	1				False
Female	DYSURIA	5	9.41	4.05	21.86	True
Female	NAUSEA	114	6.99	5.65	8.65	True
Female	DYSPEPSIA	21	7.42	4.81	11.46	True
Female	THINKING ABNORMAL	2				False

sex	pt	a	ror	ror_lower95	ror_upper95	signal
Female	TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	10	6.91	3.74	12.75	True
Female	HYPERHIDROSIS	13	5.95	3.46	10.24	True
Female	CONSTIPATION	42	7.18	5.23	9.85	True
Female	COLD SWEAT	2				False
Female	HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	4	9.51	3.75	24.12	True
Female	GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	1	7.33	4.54	11.83	True
Female	DRY MOUTH	9	4.08	2.14	7.76	True
Female	VISION BLURRED	16	4.81	2.94	7.87	True
Female	EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	0				False
Female	MOVEMENT DISORDER	1				False
Female	PRODUCT SUPPLY ISSUE	0				False
Female	INCREASED APPETITE	5	8.81	3.79	20.45	True
Female	SEDATION	3	3.78	1.32	10.83	True
Female	AGGRESSION	0				False
Female	RETCHING	1				False

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eTable 28. Age-Stratified Disproportionality

age_group	pt	a	ror	ror_lower95	ror_upper95	signal
<65	AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	2				False
<65	VIOLENCE- RELATED SYMPTOM	1				False
<65	DROOLING	18	77.89	48.26	125.72	True
<65	URINARY RETENTION	45	55.67	40.89	75.79	True
<65	TACHYPHRENIA	3	28.62	9.86	83.01	True
<65	HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	14	22.76	13.45	38.52	True
<65	SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	9	23.56	12.33	45.03	True
<65	VOMITING PROJECTILE	1				False
<65	INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	2				False
<65	NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	3	25.38	8.76	73.5	True
<65	PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	9	8.28	4.35	15.75	True
<65	PARANOIA	7	14.01	6.79	28.91	True
<65	SEDATION COMPLICATION	0				False
<65	MANIA	6	11.56	5.31	25.13	True
<65	AKATHISIA	3	6.11	2.13	17.52	True
<65	ANGER	9	10.77	5.66	20.51	True
<65	SCHIZOPHRENIA	1				False
<65	VOMITING	126	7.66	6.3	9.31	True
<65	ANURIA	1				False
<65	HICCUPS	3	15.18	5.27	43.74	True
<65	DELUSION	3	9.39	3.27	26.96	True
<65	DYSURIA	7	7.82	3.8	16.11	True
<65	NAUSEA	133	5.68	4.69	6.88	True
<65	DYSPEPSIA	36	9.25	6.61	12.94	True
<65	THINKING ABNORMAL	4	10.54	4.15	26.77	True

age_group	pt	a	ror	ror_lower95	ror_upper95	signal
<65	TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	14	4.93	2.92	8.3	True
<65	HYPERHIDROSIS	30	7.34	5.09	10.57	True
<65	CONSTIPATION	66	9.67	7.49	12.47	True
<65	COLD SWEAT	5	9.15	3.94	21.25	True
<65	HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	7	12.47	6.04	25.73	True
<65	GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	26	8.06	5.46	11.91	True
<65	DRY MOUTH	21	6.91	4.49	10.64	True
<65	VISION BLURRED	27	6.39	4.36	9.37	True
<65	EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	2				False
<65	MOVEMENT DISORDER	4	4.79	1.89	12.14	True
<65	PRODUCT SUPPLY ISSUE	3	7.99	2.78	22.92	True
<65	INCREASED APPETITE	5	5.97	2.57	13.86	True
<65	SEDATION	4	2.1	0.83	5.31	False
<65	AGGRESSION	7	4.81	2.34	9.89	True
<65	RETCHING	3	4.56	1.59	13.06	True

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eTable 29. Reporter-Stratified Disproportionality

reporter_group	pt	a	ror	ror_lower95	ror_upper95	signal
HCP	AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	3	677.62	184.38	2490.3	True
HCP	VIOLENCE- RELATED SYMPTOM	1				False
HCP	DROOLING	14	65.37	38.36	111.38	True
HCP	URINARY RETENTION	53	48.61	36.62	64.53	True
HCP	TACHYPHRENIA	1				False
HCP	HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	10	17.72	9.59	32.73	True
HCP	SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	10	28.66	15.48	53.07	True
HCP	VOMITING PROJECTILE	4	55.32	21.46	142.6	True
HCP	INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	0				False
HCP	NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	1				False
HCP	PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	18	18.04	11.33	28.72	True
HCP	PARANOIA	5	14.65	6.3	34.07	True
HCP	SEDATION COMPLICATION	3	18.7	6.49	53.86	True
HCP	MANIA	5	12.07	5.2	28.05	True
HCP	AKATHISIA	2				False
HCP	ANGER	4	12.58	4.96	31.94	True
HCP	SCHIZOPHRENIA	6	9.4	4.33	20.4	True
HCP	VOMITING	107	8.16	6.64	10.03	True
HCP	ANURIA	1				False
HCP	HICCUPS	3	13.96	4.85	40.12	True
HCP	DELUSION	5	13.15	5.66	30.56	True
HCP	DYSURIA	1				False
HCP	NAUSEA	158	9.6	8.04	11.46	True
HCP	DYSPEPSIA	10	4.04	2.19	7.44	True
HCP	THINKING ABNORMAL	1				False

reporter_group	pt	a	ror	ror_lower95	ror_upper95	signal
HCP	TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	20	7.48	4.81	11.61	True
HCP	HYPERHIDROSIS	12	3.99	2.28	6.99	True
HCP	CONSTIPATION	49	10.01	7.49	13.38	True
HCP	COLD SWEAT	1				False
HCP	HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	3	4.5	1.57	12.89	True
HCP	GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	1	6.3	3.8	10.43	True
HCP	DRY MOUTH	13	5.23	3.05	8.97	True
HCP	VISION BLURRED	23	6.38	4.22	9.63	True
HCP	EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	1				False
HCP	MOVEMENT DISORDER	3	4.98	1.74	14.27	True
HCP	PRODUCT SUPPLY ISSUE	1				False
HCP	INCREASED APPETITE	5	16.62	7.14	38.67	True
HCP	SEDATION	7	3.45	1.68	7.1	True
HCP	AGGRESSION	6	5.16	2.38	11.18	True
HCP	RETCHING	2				False

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eTable 30. E-Values for Unmeasured Confounding

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	E-value	E-value CI
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	3	207.13	66.85	413.76	133.19
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	3	81.71	27.69	162.92	54.88
DROOLING	30	60.98	42.25	121.46	84.0
URINARY RETENTION	92	44.03	35.55	87.55	70.59
TACHYPHRENIA	4	25.98	10.2	51.46	19.89
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	25	25.11	16.91	49.72	33.31
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	15	23.77	14.34	47.03	28.17
VOMITING PROJECTILE	6	23.37	10.74	46.24	20.97
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	3	20.47	7.11	40.44	13.7
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	3	18.06	6.28	35.62	12.04
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	26	15.31	10.4	30.1	20.28
PARANOIA	12	14.06	8.03	27.62	15.55
SEDATION COMPLICATION	3	13.98	4.87	27.45	9.21
MANIA	8	10.55	5.36	20.58	10.19
AKATHISIA	7	10.43	5.07	20.34	9.62
ANGER	13	9.24	5.4	17.96	10.26
SCHIZOPHRENIA	8	8.67	4.41	16.83	8.29
VOMITING	239	8.44	7.35	16.37	14.17
ANURIA	3	8.06	2.81	15.6	5.07
HICCUPS	4	8.03	3.17	15.54	5.8
DELUSION	8	7.61	3.87	14.71	7.21
DYSURIA	16	7.58	4.66	14.64	8.79
NAUSEA	314	7.54	6.65	14.57	12.79
DYSPEPSIA	51	7.2	5.44	13.87	10.36
THINKING ABNORMAL	5	7.13	3.08	13.74	5.61
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE	35	6.96	4.98	13.4	9.44
HYPERHIDROSIS	46	6.55	4.89	12.58	9.24
CONSTIPATION	110	6.46	5.32	12.39	10.1
COLD SWEAT	6	6.27	2.9	12.02	5.24
HALLUCINATION, VISUAL	10	6.26	3.41	12.0	6.27
GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	36	6.23	4.48	11.93	8.42
DRY MOUTH	35	6.21	4.45	11.9	8.36
VISION BLURRED	50	5.65	4.26	10.78	7.99
EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER	3	4.97	1.74	9.41	2.87
MOVEMENT DISORDER	9	4.94	2.61	9.35	4.65
PRODUCT SUPPLY ISSUE	4	4.88	1.93	9.24	3.27
INCREASED APPETITE	8	4.82	2.45	9.11	4.34
SEDATION	12	4.74	2.71	8.95	4.87

PT	n	ROR	ROR LCI	E-value	E-value CI
AGGRESSION	11	4.71	2.64	8.9	4.71
RETCHING	6	4.5	2.08	8.46	3.57
ADVERSE EVENT	24	4.4	2.95	8.27	5.35
ABNORMAL BEHAVIOUR	5	4.23	1.83	7.94	3.06
TACHYCARDIA	22	3.88	2.56	7.22	4.55
HEART RATE INCREASED	24	3.75	2.51	6.96	4.46
SUICIDAL IDEATION	18	3.53	2.23	6.51	3.88
HYPERSOMNIA	6	3.42	1.58	6.29	2.54
DYSKINESIA	7	3.25	1.58	5.95	2.54
GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDER	30	3.13	2.18	5.7	3.79
PRODUCT ADMINISTRATION ERROR	6	3.0	1.38	5.44	2.12
AGITATION	10	2.95	1.61	5.36	2.6
THERAPEUTIC RESPONSE UNEXPECTED	6	2.79	1.29	5.03	1.9
TREMOR	23	2.62	1.74	4.68	2.88
SOMNOLENCE	32	2.58	1.82	4.61	3.05
HALLUCINATION	14	2.47	1.47	4.38	2.31
ABDOMINAL DISCOMFORT	28	2.3	1.59	4.03	2.56
DYSPHAGIA	14	2.3	1.37	4.02	2.08

eTable 31. CYP2D6 Inhibitor Co-Medication Analysis

PT
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM
DROOLING
URINARY RETENTION
TACHYPHRENIA
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION
VOMITING PROJECTILE
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER
PARANOIA
SEDATION COMPLICATION
MANIA
AKATHISIA
ANGER
SCHIZOPHRENIA
VOMITING
ANURIA
HICCUPS
DELUSION
DYSURIA
NAUSEA
DYSPEPSIA
THINKING ABNORMAL
TREATMENT NONCOMPLIANCE
HYPERHIDROSIS
CONSTIPATION
COLD SWEAT
HALLUCINATION, VISUAL
GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE
DRY MOUTH
VISION BLURRED
EXTRAPYRAMIDAL DISORDER
MOVEMENT DISORDER
PRODUCT SUPPLY ISSUE
INCREASED APPETITE
SEDATION

PT

AGGRESSION

RETCHING

ADVERSE EVENT

ABNORMAL BEHAVIOUR

TACHYCARDIA

HEART RATE INCREASED

SUICIDAL IDEATION

HYPERSOMNIA

DYSKINESIA

GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDER

PRODUCT ADMINISTRATION ERROR

AGITATION

THERAPEUTIC RESPONSE UNEXPECTED

TREMOR

SOMNOLENCE

HALLUCINATION

ABDOMINAL DISCOMFORT

DYSPHAGIA

eTable 32. Sequential Signal Detection

PT	Through	n	ROR	LCI	UCI	Signal
NAUSEA	2024Q4	39	9.8	6.83	14.06	True
VOMITING	2024Q4	34	12.83	8.79	18.73	True
CONSTIPATION	2024Q4	12	7.69	4.31	13.72	True
URINARY RETENTION	2024Q4	12	61.27	34.14	109.96	True
DYSPEPSIA	2024Q4	2				False
DRY MOUTH	2024Q4	5	9.49	4.05	22.26	True
TACHYCARDIA	2024Q4	7	12.21	5.85	25.48	True
DROOLING	2024Q4	5	108.52	45.45	259.15	True
HYPERHIDROSIS	2024Q4	5	6.87	2.93	16.1	True
VISION BLURRED	2024Q4	12	14.43	8.08	25.76	True
AKATHISIA	2024Q4	1				False
TREMOR	2024Q4	3	3.54	1.23	10.23	True
NAUSEA	2025Q1	110	8.48	6.85	10.49	True
VOMITING	2025Q1	90	10.23	8.13	12.86	True
CONSTIPATION	2025Q1	37	7.26	5.19	10.13	True
URINARY RETENTION	2025Q1	27	41.4	28.03	61.14	True
DYSPEPSIA	2025Q1	11	5.29	2.95	9.51	True
DRY MOUTH	2025Q1	15	8.38	5.05	13.93	True
TACHYCARDIA	2025Q1	10	5.53	3.0	10.21	True
DROOLING	2025Q1	12	76.99	43.27	136.98	True
HYPERHIDROSIS	2025Q1	15	6.6	3.98	10.97	True
VISION BLURRED	2025Q1	19	6.9	4.38	10.87	True
AKATHISIA	2025Q1	1				False
TREMOR	2025Q1	6	2.09	0.97	4.54	False
NAUSEA	2025Q2	163	7.62	6.41	9.06	True
VOMITING	2025Q2	146	10.35	8.64	12.39	True
CONSTIPATION	2025Q2	54	6.48	4.92	8.54	True
URINARY RETENTION	2025Q2	48	44.6	33.2	59.9	True
DYSPEPSIA	2025Q2	26	7.66	5.2	11.3	True
DRY MOUTH	2025Q2	21	7.37	4.8	11.33	True
TACHYCARDIA	2025Q2	14	4.7	2.8	7.92	True
DROOLING	2025Q2	20	75.62	48.19	118.67	True
HYPERHIDROSIS	2025Q2	22	6.06	3.98	9.23	True
VISION BLURRED	2025Q2	27	6.09	4.16	8.91	True
AKATHISIA	2025Q2	2				False
TREMOR	2025Q2	10	2.15	1.17	3.96	True
NAUSEA	2025Q3	244	7.78	6.74	8.97	True
VOMITING	2025Q3	194	9.25	7.92	10.8	True

PT	Through	n	ROR	LCI	UCI	Signal
CONSTIPATION	2025Q3	84	6.6	5.28	8.24	True
URINARY RETENTION	2025Q3	70	44.44	34.78	56.77	True
DYSPEPSIA	2025Q3	36	6.88	4.94	9.57	True
DRY MOUTH	2025Q3	26	6.13	4.17	9.02	True
TACHYCARDIA	2025Q3	17	4.05	2.52	6.5	True
DROOLING	2025Q3	25	65.07	43.53	97.27	True
HYPERHIDROSIS	2025Q3	39	7.29	5.3	10.03	True
VISION BLURRED	2025Q3	39	5.83	4.24	8.02	True
AKATHISIA	2025Q3	5	9.57	4.13	22.19	True
TREMOR	2025Q3	15	2.26	1.37	3.74	True
NAUSEA	2025Q4	314	7.54	6.65	8.55	True
VOMITING	2025Q4	239	8.44	7.35	9.7	True
CONSTIPATION	2025Q4	110	6.46	5.32	7.84	True
URINARY RETENTION	2025Q4	92	44.03	35.55	54.53	True
DYSPEPSIA	2025Q4	51	7.2	5.44	9.51	True
DRY MOUTH	2025Q4	35	6.21	4.45	8.67	True
TACHYCARDIA	2025Q4	22	3.88	2.56	5.88	True
DROOLING	2025Q4	30	60.98	42.25	88.01	True
HYPERHIDROSIS	2025Q4	46	6.55	4.89	8.78	True
VISION BLURRED	2025Q4	50	5.65	4.26	7.49	True
AKATHISIA	2025Q4	7	10.42	5.07	21.43	True
TREMOR	2025Q4	23	2.62	1.74	3.94	True

eTable 33. Time-Stratified Disproportionality

period	pt	n	ror	ror_lower95	ror_upper95	signal
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	NAUSEA	110	8.48	6.85	10.49	True
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	VOMITING	90	10.23	8.13	12.86	True
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	CONSTIPATION	37	7.26	5.19	10.13	True
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	URINARY RETENTION	27	41.4	28.03	61.14	True
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	TACHYCARDIA	10	5.53	3.0	10.21	True
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	DROOLING	12	76.99	43.27	136.98	True
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	DRY MOUTH	15	8.38	5.05	13.93	True
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	DYSPEPSIA	11	5.29	2.95	9.51	True
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	VISION BLURRED	19	6.9	4.38	10.87	True
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	HYPERHIDROSIS	15	6.6	3.98	10.97	True
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	AKATHISIA	0				False
early (Q4'24–Q1'25)	TREMOR	6	2.09	0.97	4.54	False
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	NAUSEA	204	7.09	6.07	8.28	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	VOMITING	149	7.61	6.39	9.07	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	CONSTIPATION	73	6.1	4.8	7.74	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	URINARY RETENTION	65	45.31	35.11	58.48	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	TACHYCARDIA	12	3.19	1.83	5.58	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	DROOLING	18	54.51	34.06	87.22	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	DRY MOUTH	20	5.28	3.4	8.19	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	DYSPEPSIA	40	8.06	5.88	11.05	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	VISION BLURRED	31	5.12	3.59	7.31	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	HYPERHIDROSIS	31	6.61	4.63	9.44	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	AKATHISIA	6	12.9	5.94	28.01	True
late (Q2'25–Q4'25)	TREMOR	17	2.99	1.86	4.8	True

eTable 34. Signal Masking Analysis

masked_by	pt	a_original	a_adjusted	ror_original	ror_adjusted	ror_lower95_adjusted	ror_change_pct	unmasked
NAUSEA	DIZZINESS	61	39	1.99	1.63	1.18	-18.25	True
NAUSEA	ABDOMINAL PAIN UPPER	28	22	1.92	1.95	1.28	1.3	True
NAUSEA	ANGIOEDEMA	6	6	2.22	2.85	1.32	28.46	True
NAUSEA	INSOMNIA	28	25	1.85	2.13	1.44	15.13	True
NAUSEA	ORTHOSTATIC HYPOTEN- SION	3	3	3.6	4.62	1.62	28.38	True
NAUSEA	MUSCLE TWITCHING	3	3	2.86	3.68	1.29	28.38	True
NAUSEA	BLEPHAROSPASM	3	3	3.54	4.55	1.59	28.38	True
NAUSEA	OFF LABEL USE	97	82	0.91	0.99	0.79	9.24	False
NAUSEA	ADVERSE DRUG REACTION	9	9	1.15	1.48	0.78	28.53	False
NAUSEA	PALPITATIONS	10	7	1.49	1.37	0.67	-8.42	False
NAUSEA	CONFUSIONAL STATE	12	9	1.28	1.25	0.66	-2.53	False
NAUSEA	ABDOMINAL PAIN	14	5	0.85	0.41	0.18	-51.6	False
NAUSEA	FEELING ABNORMAL	13	10	1.16	1.16	0.63	-0.22	False
NAUSEA	WEIGHT DECREASED	23	18	1.2	1.21	0.76	1.01	False
NAUSEA	HYPERTENSION	18	16	1.23	1.41	0.87	14.64	False
NAUSEA	BLOOD PRESSURE INCREASED	15	13	1.47	1.65	0.96	11.88	False
NAUSEA	DECREASED APPETITE	16	9	0.92	0.68	0.36	-26.36	False
NAUSEA	CHEST PAIN	16	15	1.6	1.93	1.17	20.8	True
NAUSEA	DYSPHONIA	6	3	1.54	1.06	0.37	-31.02	False
NAUSEA	BRAIN FOG	7	5	1.52	1.43	0.62	-5.95	False
NAUSEA	DRUG INTOL- ERANCE	9	5	1.23	0.91	0.39	-25.86	False
NAUSEA	DEHYDRATION	9	4	1.22	0.74	0.29	-39.39	False
NAUSEA	CHILLS	8	6	1.17	1.15	0.53	-1.91	False

masked_by	pt	a_original	a_adjusted	ror_original	ror_adjusted	ror_lower95_adjusted	ror_change_pct	unmasked
NAUSEA	THERAPY	8	8	1.58	2.03	1.03	28.5	True
NAUSEA	NON-RESPONDER							
NAUSEA	MUSCULAR WEAKNESS	8	7	1.13	1.28	0.63	13.28	False
NAUSEA	LETHARGY	4	4	1.42	1.82	0.72	28.41	False
NAUSEA	INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION	5	4	1.53	1.61	0.64	4.98	False
NAUSEA	NIGHT SWEATS	5	3	1.85	1.51	0.53	-18.42	False
NAUSEA	COMPLETED SUICIDE	5	5	1.8	2.31	1.0	28.43	False
NAUSEA	FEELING HOT	5	5	1.48	1.9	0.82	28.43	False
NAUSEA	IRRITABILITY	5	4	1.9	2.0	0.79	4.98	False
NAUSEA	PRODUCT USE COMPLAINT	4	4	1.87	2.4	0.95	28.4	False
NAUSEA	POLLAKIURIA	4	4	1.64	2.11	0.83	28.41	False
NAUSEA	SPEECH DISORDER	4	3	1.54	1.53	0.54	-0.22	False
NAUSEA	VERTIGO	4	2	1.27				False
NAUSEA	PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION ISSUE	3	3	1.54	1.98	0.69	28.38	False
NAUSEA	RESTLESSNESS	4	4	2.22	2.85	1.13	28.4	True
NAUSEA	DISTURBANCE IN ATTENTION	4	3	1.72	1.72	0.6	-0.22	False
NAUSEA	THROAT TIGHTNESS	3	3	2.09	2.68	0.94	28.38	False
NAUSEA	PHARYNGEAL SWELLING	3	2	2.77				False

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eTable 35. Dose-Response Analysis

pt	dose_group	n_events	n_total	pct	fisher_p
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	low	0	50	0.0	1.0
AMPHETAMINES POSITIVE	high	0	47	0.0	1.0
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	low	0	50	0.0	1.0
VIOLENCE-RELATED SYMPTOM	high	0	47	0.0	1.0
DROOLING	low	3	50	6.0	1.0
DROOLING	high	3	47	6.38	1.0
URINARY RETENTION	low	6	50	12.0	0.74
URINARY RETENTION	high	4	47	8.51	0.74
TACHYPHRENIA	low	0	50	0.0	1.0
TACHYPHRENIA	high	0	47	0.0	1.0
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	low	3	50	6.0	1.0
HALLUCINATION, AUDITORY	high	3	47	6.38	1.0
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	low	0	50	0.0	1.0
SALIVARY HYPERSECRETION	high	0	47	0.0	1.0
VOMITING PROJECTILE	low	0	50	0.0	1.0
VOMITING PROJECTILE	high	0	47	0.0	1.0
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	low	0	50	0.0	1.0
INTRUSIVE THOUGHTS	high	0	47	0.0	1.0
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	low	0	50	0.0	1.0
NEGATIVE THOUGHTS	high	0	47	0.0	1.0
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	low	1	50	2.0	1.0
PSYCHOTIC DISORDER	high	0	47	0.0	1.0
PARANOIA	low	2	50	4.0	1.0
PARANOIA	high	2	47	4.26	1.0
SEDATION COMPLICATION	low	0	50	0.0	1.0
SEDATION COMPLICATION	high	0	47	0.0	1.0
MANIA	low	0	50	0.0	1.0
MANIA	high	0	47	0.0	1.0
AKATHISIA	low	0	50	0.0	0.48
AKATHISIA	high	1	47	2.13	0.48
ANGER	low	1	50	2.0	1.0
ANGER	high	1	47	2.13	1.0
SCHIZOPHRENIA	low	1	50	2.0	1.0
SCHIZOPHRENIA	high	1	47	2.13	1.0
VOMITING	low	9	50	18.0	1.0
VOMITING	high	8	47	17.02	1.0
ANURIA	low	0	50	0.0	1.0
ANURIA	high	0	47	0.0	1.0

pt	dose_group	n_events	n_total	pct	fisher_p
HICCUPS	low	1	50	2.0	1.0
HICCUPS	high	1	47	2.13	1.0

eTable 36. Positive and Negative Control Validation

Drug	PT	n	ROR	LCI	Signal	Type	Expected
olanzapine	WEIGHT INCREASED	432	5.58	5.06	True	positive	Expected strong signal
olanzapine	HYPERGLYCAEMIA	31	3.13	2.2	True	positive	Expected signal
olanzapine	DIABETES MELLITUS	59	2.93	2.27	True	positive	Expected signal
risperidone	HYPERPROLACTINEMIA	40	208.64	167.85	True	positive	Expected strong signal
risperidone	TARDIVE DYSKINESIA	65	27.03	20.96	True	positive	Expected signal
quetiapine	SOMNOLENCE	519	6.9	6.3	True	positive	Expected strong signal
quetiapine	WEIGHT INCREASED	599	5.96	5.48	True	positive	Expected signal
aripiprazole	AKATHISIA	239	119.34	102.76	True	positive	Expected signal
olanzapine	URINARY RETENTION	72	6.64	5.25	True	negative	Not expected
aripiprazole	WEIGHT INCREASED	367	5.96	5.36	True	negative	Weak/no signal expected
quetiapine	HYPERPROLACTINEMIA	55	39.06	29.27	True	negative	Weak signal expected

eTable 37. System Organ Class Signal Aggregation

SOC	PTs	Signals	Reports	Max ROR	Median ROR
Gastrointestinal disorders	14	12	956	60.98	6.83
Psychiatric disorders	13	12	152	81.71	10.55
Nervous system disorders	8	6	170	25.98	3.68
Renal and urinary disorders	2	2	108	44.03	25.8
Cardiac disorders	1	1	22	3.88	3.88
Eye disorders	1	1	50	5.65	5.65
General disorders	3	1	90	6.96	0.4
Skin and subcutaneous tissue disorders	1	1	46	6.55	6.55
Investigations	2	0	25	1.47	1.04
Product issues	1	0	97	0.91	0.91
Vascular disorders	1	0	18	1.23	1.23

eTable 38. Outcome Severity Comparison

Drug	N	Death %	Hosp %
Cobenfy	1423	1.34	7.52
Olanzapine	6926	9.76	46.4
Risperidone	6254	5.9	35.58
Aripiprazole	5516	8.18	38.45
Quetiapine	9074	24.62	49.25
Lurasidone	806	3.6	37.34
Brexpiprazole	1288	26.71	27.64

eTable 39. Sensitivity Analyses Summary (Formerly Table 4)

Analysis	Restriction	n	Signals	Key Observation
Primary	PS + SS	1,423	56	Reference
PS only	PS	1,416	56 (100%)	Identical
US only	US country	1,408	56 (100%)	Consistent
HCP only	MD/PH/OT/HP/RN	706	41 (73%)	Smaller n
Serious only	DE/LT/HO/DS/CA/RI	131	14 (25%)	Core GI robust
No concomitant AP	Excl. concomitant	1,298	53 (95%)	Drooling: 61->60

eTable 40. Time-to-Onset Weibull Parameters (Formerly Table 5)

PT	n	Median TTO (d)	Weibull beta	Scale	% <30d
Urinary retention	23	0.0	0.91	4.3	100.0
Nausea	89	1.0	0.59	11.7	91.0
Vomiting	93	2.0	0.59	15.7	90.3
Constipation	47	1.0	0.66	10.5	93.6
Dyspepsia	31	3.0	0.85	11.1	93.5
Hyperhidrosis	24	0.5	0.71	8.8	95.8
Dizziness	35	1.0	0.56	15.4	91.4

All beta < 1 = early-onset, decreasing hazard.

Supplementary Figures

Case Selection Flow Diagram

Figure 1: **eFigure 1.** FAERS case identification and deduplication flow diagram.

Outcome Severity: Cobenfy vs Active Comparators

Figure 2: **eFigure 2.** Outcome severity distribution across xanomeline-trospium and active comparators.

Case Selection Flow Diagram

Figure 3: eFigure 3. Case selection flow diagram (formerly Figure 0).
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Cumulative Sequential Signal Detection: ROR by Quarter

Figure 4: eFigure 4. Cumulative sequential signal detection, Q4 2024 through Q4 2025 (formerly Figure 3). Shaded areas = 95% CIs.

Time-to-Onset: Weibull Cumulative Distribution
($\beta < 1$ indicates early-onset, decreasing hazard)

Figure 5: **eFigure 5.** Time-to-onset Weibull cumulative probability (formerly Figure 4). All beta < 1 = early-onset.

Label Concordance Analysis: FAERS Signals vs FDA Prescribing Information

Figure 6: **eFigure 6.** Label concordance analysis (formerly Figure 5).